

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE PARTICIPATION OF CITIZENS IN THE LOCAL GOVERNANCE PROCESS OF THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

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Abstract

The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is one of the special administrative territorial units of Azerbaijan, and ensuring the participation of citizens in elections to local self-government bodies is of particular importance here. Local self-government is an important mechanism that allows citizens to directly or indirectly participate in democratic governance. In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, this process is carried out in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Law "On Municipalities" and other normative and legal acts.

This article examines the participation of citizens in municipal elections in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and the participation of elected representatives (municipal members) in solving issues of local importance by representing the interests of citizens.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, citizen, local self-government, municipal, municipal elections opinion poll

Introduction

Elections, one of the most important institutions of democracy, occupy an important place in the formation of civil society. Because they are a direct and highest expression of the will of the people, include the holding of free and democratic elections to state authorities and local self-government bodies, as well as expressing their attitude to the most important issues of public life through universal suffrage. Elections are a widespread form of citizens' participation in public life and state affairs almost everywhere in the world. Elections have a major impact on the formation of political culture, legal consciousness and society, and the unification of the will of the people around national interests. Elections are of particular importance among general legal relations and play a key role in ensuring and developing democracy, which is also related to the function of elections to involve citizens in state administration. All this shows that the right to vote is of particular importance among other constitutional rights of citizens.

The article examines and scientifically analyzes the organization and functioning of local self-government bodies based on the will of the people.

The importance of citizens' participation in the local governance process

The right to elect and be elected to state and local self-government bodies (municipalities) is one of the basic constitutional rights of every citizen. Except for the cases specified in Article 56 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Election Code, every citizen of Azerbaijan who has reached the age of 18 by the day of the Milli Majlis, Presidential and municipal elections have the right to vote, participate in a referendum, observe the election process, participate in pre-election campaigning and election campaigns provided for in the Election Code. Along with this, he also has the right to participate in the preparation of a referendum and participate in the holding of elections, which is part of his active right to vote.

In accordance with Part II of Article 56 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, persons confirmed by a court decision as incompetent are deprived of the right to participate in elections, as well as in a referendum, as well as the right to active vote.

The electoral legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan has established the principles of participation in elections. Thus, citizens of the country participate in elections on the basis of universal, equal and direct suffrage by secret and personal voting. Citizens' participation in elections and referendums is free and voluntary. No one has the right to pressure a citizen of the Republic of Azerbaijan to participate in elections or referendums, and no one can prevent him from freely expressing his will. Diplomatic missions and consular offices of the Republic of Azerbaijan must assist citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan living outside the country in exercising their rights stipulated in Articles 3 and 56 of our Constitution during elections. The legal basis of local self-government in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic (NAR) is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan and national legislation on the activities of municipalities. Due to the special administrative status of the autonomous republic, local self-government here is distinguished by some features. The legislative basis regulates the participation of citizens in local-level governance and the activities of municipalities.

1. "According to the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, local self-government is considered a part of the state administration system of the country and is implemented through municipalities to ensure the interests of the local population." Article 144 of the Constitution defines the legal basis of local self-government and its main principles. (8)

2. Taking into account the special status of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the Constitution and laws of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic have been brought into line with the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

3. The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic has autonomy within the Republic of Azerbaijan and has its own legislative body, the Supreme Assembly. This body may adopt special laws on local self-government.

One of the main forms of citizen participation in the legal framework of local self-government is municipal elections. Municipal members are elected for a five-year term and their main task is to represent local interests. Municipal elections are also held in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in accordance with the Election Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, citizens' participation in local self-government is mainly realized through municipalities. Citizens participate in municipal elections and elect their representatives. Elected representatives (municipal members) represent the interests of citizens and participate in resolving issues of local importance. These forms of participation can be listed as follows:

1. Participation in municipal elections. Citizens elect municipal members at the local level and directly influence the activities of municipalities.

2. Public discussions: By involving citizens in municipal discussions, they can express their opinions on issues implemented at the local level. This increases the ability of citizens to influence the adoption of specific decisions.

3. Coordination of decisions with the public: It is important to take into account citizens' proposals when implementing projects of local importance. For example, when making decisions on infrastructure projects, when organizing social services, citizens' participation and their proposals are important.

4. Citizens' applications and requests. Citizens can apply to municipalities with various applications and proposals. This ensures their more active participation in local governance and direct influence on solving their problems.

Municipal elections are one of the main forms of citizens' participation in the legal sphere of local self-government. Municipal members are elected for a term of five years and their main task is to represent local interests. Municipal elections are also held in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in accordance with the Election Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan. In the Republic of Azerbaijan, members of local self-government bodies are elected in multi-mandate constituencies using a proportional majority system. The following number of municipal members are elected by constituencies.

In areas with a population of less than 500, the number of municipal members is 5. In areas with a population of 500 to 999, this number is 7, and in areas with a population of 1,000 to 4,999, 9 municipal members are elected. In areas with a population of 5,000 to 9,999, 11 municipal members are appointed, and in areas with a population of 10,000 to 19,999, 13 municipal members are appointed. In areas with a population of 20,000 to 49,999, the number of municipal members is 15, in areas with a population of 50,000 to 99,999, 17, and in areas with a population of 100,000 to 299,999, 19 members.

In order to be registered as a candidate for municipal membership in the relevant electoral district, each citizen nominated must collect a certain number of voter signatures in order to gain the right to participate in the election. In areas with a population of more than 99,999, this number is 150, in areas with a population of more than 49,999, 100, in areas with a population of more than 19,999, 75, in areas with a population of more than 9,999, 50, in areas with a population of more than 4,999, 30, and in areas with a population of less than 4,999, 15 signatures are required.

Regarding the municipal elections held in the Republic of Azerbaijan, I can note that the first municipal elections in the Republic of Azerbaijan were held in 1999. [6].

During these elections, 74 election districts and 4,683 precinct election commissions were established. 90.5 thousand people participated in the organization of the elections. A number of parties registered by the Ministry of Justice actively participated in them. The composition of the precinct election commissions included 18 percent and 30 percent representatives of political parties and public organizations, respectively. The composition of the precinct election commissions included more than 5 thousand candidates from 21 political parties. 35.6 thousand people were registered as candidates in 2667 municipalities. 52.6 percent of the country's 4 million 312 thousand 265 voters voted in the election. The first municipal elections in the Republic of Azerbaijan were held in 1999. During these elections, 74 election districts and 4683 precinct election commissions were established. 90.5 thousand people participated in the organization of the elections. A number of parties registered by the Ministry of Justice actively participated in them. The composition of the precinct election commissions included 18 percent and 30 percent representatives of political parties and public organizations, respectively. The composition of the precinct election commissions included more than 5 thousand candidates from 21 political parties. 35.6 thousand people were registered as candidates in 2667 municipalities. 52.6 percent of the country's 4 million 312 thousand 265 voters voted in the election. 20456 municipal members were elected in the elections. [6].

In the next municipal elections held on December 17, 2004, 4 million 551 thousand 346 people had the right to vote. Of these, 2 million 109 thousand 267 people voted in the municipal elections - 46.34%. In the municipal elections, 38,041 registered candidates were elected to 21,613 vacant seats in 2,731 municipalities.

A number of different features were noticeable in the next municipal elections held in December 2009. In most areas, the process of enlarging municipalities took place and the new municipal division was brought closer to the scale of local territorial administrative units that existed in the Soviet era. As a result of this change, instead of the financial expenses of the chairman and staff of several village municipal councils, only the financial expenses of the chairman and staff of the generalized municipal council were provided. In the municipal elections held in 2009, approximately 31 thousand candidates competed for 15,682 seats in 1,718 municipalities. 16,755 candidates were nominated by

political parties, 14,733 individually, and 147 by initiative groups. 1,466,734 voters participated in the elections, which constituted 32.04 percent of the total number of voters. As a result, the number of candidates elected as municipal members was 15,591.

Repeated, additional, and new municipal elections were also completed in Azerbaijan. These elections were held in 1,169 polling stations, and voting was held for 464 seats in 330 municipalities in 86 constituencies. In total, 1,549 candidates participated in the struggle for municipal membership. Among them, candidates from 9 political parties, as well as 709 independent candidates, were registered. 305 of the candidates were women. 43.45 percent of the candidates had higher education, 39.06 percent had secondary education, and 17.11 percent had secondary vocational education. The voter list included 1,155,864 people. 9,923 observers were registered to monitor the elections.

The Central Election Commission of the Republic of Azerbaijan (CEC) decided to hold the next municipal elections on December 23, 2014, by its decision No. 4/25 adopted on October 21, 2014. After the elections were scheduled, the "Main Action Plan for the Preparation and Conduct of Municipal Elections" was approved, and all work related to the organization of the elections was carried out in accordance with this plan.

In order to conduct the elections, which are scheduled to elect 15,035 members to 1,607 municipalities across the country, the CEC carried out the process of clarifying the voter lists from the beginning of the year to the end of May. According to the law "On the establishment of new municipalities through the merger of municipalities in the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated May 30, 2014, 110 municipalities belonging to 28 electoral districts were abolished and the total number of municipalities in the country was determined as 1607. In accordance with the requirements of creating favorable conditions for voters, adapting to local conditions and not violating the boundaries of electoral districts, 113 new polling stations were established in accordance with the Election Code. [6].

Since the term of office of the municipalities formed as a result of the elections held on December 23, 2014 is about to expire, the Central Election Commission (CEC) discussed the issue of scheduling the next municipal elections at its meeting dated October 18, 2019 and decided to hold the elections on December 23, 2019 by the Commission's decision No. 7/24. After the elections were scheduled, the "Calendar Plan of Main Actions and Measures for the Preparation and Conduct of Municipal Elections" was approved, and measures related to the preparation and conduct of the elections were implemented based on the plan.

At the final meeting of the CEC on January 11, 2020, after discussions with the participation of international organizations and the media, it was decided to cancel the results of voting in 39 polling stations, declare the elections in 9 municipalities invalid, form the officially approved composition of 1,597 municipalities, and announce the list of elected members. [6].

Municipal elections are planned to be held at the end of 2024. In accordance with Article 213 of the Election Code, municipal elections are scheduled by the

Central Election Commission and must be officially published in the media no later than 2 days from the date of adoption of this decision.

There are many ways for citizens to participate in the formation of local self-government bodies, their decision-making processes and activities. World experience shows that different countries use different methods in this regard. For example, during elections to local self-government bodies, conducting surveys among the local population, citizens' meetings, involving citizens in the work of commissions, and other methods ensure direct or indirect participation of citizens in the work of local self-government bodies [1]

If we look at the situation in Azerbaijan, we will see that there are various laws that ensure the active participation of citizens in local governance. Chapter IV of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the Status of Municipalities" contains articles related to the direct expression of the will of citizens and other forms of local self-government. At the same time, there are various regulations on this issue in the legislation. Laws on municipal elections and local public opinion polls. [2]

One of the methods of citizens' participation in local governance is a local survey. According to the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Surveys Among the Local Population", a public opinion poll at the local level is a study of the opinions of citizens living in the region on important issues. (Article 1).

In general, a local survey expresses the free will of the residents of a municipality regarding the main tasks of local self-government. Issues of local importance, which are attributed to the competence of municipalities by the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan and legislation, may be submitted to a local public opinion poll (Article 2).

One of the methods of citizens' participation in local self-government is citizens' meetings. The law on citizens' meetings is stipulated in Article 28 of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the Status of Municipalities". According to this law, in municipalities with a population of less than 500 people, citizens may hold their own meetings in the territories of those municipalities in order to express their attitude to issues of local importance, put forward proposals, express collective opinions and make decisions. Residents of the municipality who have reached the age of 18 participate in citizens' meetings. The charter of the municipality and other decisions are adopted, changed and canceled at these meetings. Meetings are authorized when at least 25% of citizens residing in the territory of the municipality and having the right to vote attend them." [3].

One of the forms of citizen participation in the activities of municipalities is ensuring participation in the local budget process. Participation of the municipal community in the local budget process is a process of continuous interaction between civil society institutions in the region, as well as citizens. This is a process of continuous interaction between each other and local self-government bodies in the territory. [4].

Ensuring public participation in the local budget process means that people have real opportunities to express their opinions on the budget and promote their ideas about it [5]

Public participation in the local budget process:

- ✓ creates an information space regarding the local budget
- ✓ makes it relevant for both municipalities and the population;
- ✓ identifies problems and needs;
- ✓ accelerates the implementation of adopted decisions;
- ✓ promotes alternative solutions to problems and new ideas.

Public participation in the budget process provides control over the activities of municipal bodies, creates an opportunity to take into account the interests of individual social groups, and also increases the efficiency of local budget policy by taking into account the interests of communities. In addition, such participation allows citizens to exercise their right to receive information about the budget. There is no doubt that the main goal of public participation in the budget process is to ensure budget transparency and, as a result, achieve efficient use of budget funds.

The above once again guarantees the independence of municipalities in their activities. These bodies, which are not part of the state power system and exist separately from it, are the true bearers of democracy, which is the most promising and effective form of people's power.

Conclusion

1. The participation of citizens in local self-government is enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The local self-government system is one of the main mechanisms that ensure the direct participation of citizens in state administration. The democratic reforms implemented through local self-government bodies in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and the expansion of citizen participation can lead to significant scientific results in this area.

2. Strengthening the legislative framework of local self-government in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and the formation of legal regulatory mechanisms ensure more active and effective participation of citizens. In this regard, the study of the legal and institutional framework can yield scientific results.

3. The participation of citizens in local self-government affects the increase in transparency and accountability in the adoption and implementation of local decisions. The study of this topic can lead to important scientific results indicating the role of civil society in governance mechanisms.

4. Active participation of citizens in solving local problems through their own initiatives, the formation of a more democratic environment in the collective decision-making process, and the implementation of various projects in this direction can lead to significant scientific results.

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